
Morphologic Segmentation Linearity Analysis in Aesop's Fable the Crow and the Pitcher

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ABSTRACT

This study employed structural descriptive analysis to investigate the morphological segmentation linearity of the textuality in Aesop's fable, "The Crow and the Pitcher," by analyzing the lexical and grammatical morphemes of each word in the narrative reveals thirty-seven (37) lexical morphemes of twenty six (26) simple form (roots) and eleven (11) complex forms (roots with affixations) and thirty (30) grammatical morphemes broken down as follows: eight (8) prepositions, four (4) pronouns, seven (7) conjunctions, five (5) determiners, and three (3) auxiliaries. The findings indicate that "The Crow and the Pitcher" adheres to a morphological segmentation linearity, providing insight into the structural composition of the narrative. Future linguistic research is recommended to build upon these findings by further analyzing the textual composition of "The Crow and the Pitcher" to deepen our understanding of its linguistic and narrative structures.

KEYWORDS: Morphologic Analysis, Segmentation Linearity, Morphemes, Aesop's Fables, Lexical Morphemes, Grammatical Morphemes.

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INTRODUCTION

Reading is an interactive and mentally engaging process that requires readers to draw upon their personal experiences and existing knowledge to comprehend a material. Readers who are aware of word structures can better decode and read words, which is critical for reading comprehension, (Babayiğit, S., & Shapiro, L. R. 2019).

Studies by Sulistyawati, et al., (2021) has shown that the knowledge about word structure significantly contributes to better reading comprehension and vocabulary. By understanding the rules and patterns of word formation, learners can more easily decode unfamiliar words and recognize word families. This knowledge not only expands their vocabulary but also enables them to infer the meanings of new words based on their morphological components (Ghasemi & Vaez-Dalili, 2019).

This is especially true for comprehending literary text. Rousoulioti et al. (2022), suggests that Morphologic segmentation is a useful strategy for learning new words, especially for students who are learning a third language. They argued that by understanding the morphological structure of words, students can better comprehend their meaning and build their vocabulary more effectively.

According to Rice (2024), Morphological segmentation is the process of breaking down words into morphemes, the smallest meaning units in a language. Due to English having complex morphological system, morphemes can merge and change throughout word creation, and the exact morphological content of a word is frequently obscured. Segmentation may take a linear form.

Morphologic segmentation linearity is a form descriptive structural analysis that involves dissecting words into their component morphemes through sequencing their immediate constituents in a linear structure to facilitate understanding of a selection. This approach was used in various studies for instance, the descriptive structural analysis of the linearity in Aesop's fable The Farmer and The Snake by Magdato (2024), Gido & Mendoza's (2022) morphological analysis of the the Kamayo language in "Lawod ng Kamingaw" by Danny Sillada; and Chairunissa's et al (2024), affixation process in the "Second Victory" by Morris West.

Aesop's classic fable, The Crow and the Pitcher is the chosen selection for analysis of this study. It teaches learners the moral perseverance, determination, and creative thinking can help overcome seemingly insurmountable obstacles. The crow, despite initial failure, persisted in finding a solution by using pebbles to raise the water level in the pitcher, ultimately achieving his goal of drinking water.

According to Saputra (2023), fables are an effective tool for enhancing reading comprehension among high school students. Therefore, language teachers should integrate fables like the one in this study as part of instruction. This may not only provide

readers with valuable moral lessons, but may also enable English language learners to comprehend the structures of word formation and how each component contributes to the overall meaning of a text.

Research Objective

This linguistic study examines the morphological segmentation linearity of the textuality in Aesop's fable, "The Crow and the Pitcher" Specifically, the analysis delves into the lexical and grammatical morphemes of each word in the narrative, providing insight into the structural composition of the text.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Role of Morphology in Language Learning

Morphology examines the internal structure of words, focusing on how they are formed and how their meanings are related, (Yule, 2022). This field of study is crucial in teaching English vocabulary because it helps students understand how words are related and how they can be used in different contexts. Thus, knowledge morphology can improve learner's vocabulary and comprehension skills, (Jiang 2020).

Learning the rules and patterns of word creation, such as prefixes, suffixes, and compounding, allows students to decode unknown words and recognize word families with more ease. This information not only broadens their vocabulary, but also allows kids to understand new words based on their morphological components (Ghasemi and Vaez-Dalili, 2019).

Morphologic Segmentation on Reading Comprehension and Vocabulary

Morphological segmentation is the act of breaking down words into their constituent morphemes, which are the most basic units of meaning in a language (Voleti, 2023). This process involves identifying the morphemes and their relationships within a word, such as prefixes, suffixes, and roots.

Moreover, Moeng et al. (2021) discussed morphological segmentation as a process that involves decomposing words into their individual morphemes and obtaining their morphological analysis to understand the internal structure of words.

Rousoulioti et al. (2022), suggests that Morphologic segmentation is important in understanding the structure and meaning of words, as well as in various natural language processing tasks. They further claimed that it as a useful strategy for learning new words, especially for students who are learning a third language. They argued that by understanding the morphological structure of words, students can better comprehend their meaning and build their vocabulary more effectively. Their study validates de la Pena's (2019) argument that the internal structure of words affects how quickly and accurately one can identify their meaning and categorize them as nouns or verbs. The study also suggests that derivational morphemes can be processed as independent units, which facilitates comprehension and composition. This implies that our brains can break down words into their constituent parts to better understand their meaning.

Morphologic Segmentation Linearity

Morphologic segmentation linearity is a vital aspect of morphological analysis, particularly in the context comprehending literary pieces. This approach is essential for understanding the internal structure of words and their relationships within a text. Several studies were conducted using this approach to understand various selections. For instance, Quebec (2022), used this approach morphologic segmentation linearity in analysing Jose Villa's PROEM's textuality to gain insights into the poet's use of language and the underlying structure of the poem. The analysis revealed that the poem's morphemes undergo changes in terms of their class after going through the process of affixation. This change in class is crucial for understanding the poem's meaning and the poet's use of language. The study concludes that the said piece follows morphologic segmentation linearity in its free verse textuality,

Similarly, Gido, N. G., & Mendoza, R. A. (2022) conducted a study about understanding how words are formed in the Kamayo language, which is spoken in the eastern coast of Mindanao, a region in Philippines. The researchers analyzed a poem called "Lawod ng Kamingaw" by Danny Sillada to see how words are broken down into smaller parts, called morphemes. They found that the Kamayo language uses different affixes (prefixes, suffixes, and circumfixes) to change the meaning of root words. These affixes are important because they help convey the meaning of the words and are unique to the Kamayo language.

Furthermore, Chairunissa et al (2024), analyzed the affixation process in the novel "The Second Victory" by Morris West using the qualitative method by categorizing prefixes and suffixes. They argued that using novels as a medium for learning about affixation is very effective. The researchers found 15 prefixes and 89 suffixes which constitutes to 104 affixes. Moreover, their findings suggest that prefix "re" and suffix "ly" are the most common affixes in the selection.

In their study, Jamil, et al., (2022), explored the morphological affixes found in the "Forerunner" by Khalil Gibran through a descriptive mixed method. The result shows that the poetry contains 105 affixes and 99 of these are affixes. They also highlighted that affixes are used to change the meaning of words and their grammatical categories which knowledge in these aspects of word structures can help readers understand difficult words in the poetry.

These studies indicates that the researchers likely analyzed and categorized affixes found in the poetry in a systematic process, which may have include segmentation by breaking down words into their constituent parts.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study covers a linear morphologic analysis of the segmentation of the content and function words in the textuality in Aesop's Fable "The Crow and the Pitcher." The study utilized descriptive analysis and structural analysis in linguistic investigation.

According to Karpati (2022), descriptive analysis is a method of linguistic investigation that focuses on the objective description of how a language is actually used by a language community. It involves the systematic representation of phonemes, allophones, and transformations into morphemes. This approach is characterized by the consistent application of basic concepts and analytical procedures to describe the form and function of language.

According to Quebec (2022), structural analysis in linguistics involves breaking down words into smaller parts to determine their underlying meaning. The individual components that make up a word, when analyzed, contribute to understanding the overall meaning of that word. In English, many words consist of a root, prefix, and/or suffix. By examining the structure of a word and how its parts function within a sentence or phrase, linguists can analyze the word's meaning and usage.

This paper examines Aesop's timeless fable, "The Crow and the Pitcher," which has been a staple of children's literature for centuries. Aesop, a legendary Greek fabulist and storyteller, is credited with creating a collection of fables that have been passed down through generations.

Aesop's fables are distinguished by their use of anthropomorphic animal characters, which convey moral lessons that continue to resonate with readers today. These fables have been popularized by numerous writers, including Phaedrus and Jean de La Fontaine, and have been adapted into various forms of media, ensuring their enduring relevance and appeal.

Instruments

The relevance of the selection and its status as a well-regarded by literary critics and scholars prompted the researchers to choose this classic bedtime story. The fable "The Crow and the Pitcher" by Aesop. This serves as the primary source for this analysis. The theory of linear grammar by Corder forms the foundation for examining the morphological segmentation linearity of the text, as described below:

In a spell of dry weather, when the Birds could find very little to drink, a thirsty Crow found a pitcher with a little water in it. But the pitcher was high and had a narrow neck, and no matter how he tried, the Crow could not reach the water. The poor thing felt as if he must die of thirst.

Then an idea came to him. Picking up some small pebbles, he dropped them into the pitcher one by one. With each pebble the water rose a little higher until at last it was near enough so he could drink.

The text for analysis contains eight sentences. Since the study is concerned with morphological segmentation linearity, punctuation marks in the text were not included in this analysis.

Procedure

The analysis of the fable "The Crow and the Pitcher" involves three stages:

The first stage of the analysis involves idealization of raw data, which involves preparing and normalizing the verbal data to ensure it is complete, accurate, and free of errors in spelling, grammar, and punctuation. This step ensures that the data is in a suitable format for further analysis, allowing for a more comprehensive and reliable examination of the morphological structure of the words. To attain this step and ensure the accuracy of data, the instrument was adapted from the version of The Library of Congress.

The second stage involves morphological segmentation, a vital technique in natural language processing that allows for the precise identification and analysis of word structures. This technique is particularly effective in languages that employ complex morphological patterns where prefixes, suffixes, and roots are combined to form words, (Voleti, 2023). In this stage, content words within the text are segmented and categorized into their respective word classes, including nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs. Additionally, these words are further classified based on their form, which can be simple, compound, complex, or compound-complex, providing a detailed understanding of their internal structure, (Quebec, 2022).

The third stage involves the identification and analysis of grammatical morphemes, which are crucial for understanding the relationships between words in a sentence. Grammatical morphemes, such as pronouns, prepositions, determiners, conjunctions, and articles, are analyzed in terms of their constituents and functions within the sentence. These morphemes are essential for conveying meaning and relationships between lexical morphemes, and their identification and analysis provide valuable insights into the grammatical structure of the sentence.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphologic Segmentation Linearity

This comprehensive linear morphological analysis of Aesop's "The Crow and the Pitcher" delves into the morphemic segmentation of both content and function words within the text, examining the intricate affixation patterns that govern the lexical and grammatical morphemes, thereby providing a detailed understanding of the morphological structure and relationships within the text.

Lexical Morphemes: Content Words

Lexical morphemes are a fundamental unit of lexical meaning in a language, carrying meaning independently and standing alone as words. They are characterized by their independence, meaning, parts of speech, open class status, and free morpheme nature. Lexical morphemes include nouns, adjectives, and verbs, which are crucial for conveying meaning and creating new words, (Yule, 2022). Additionally, Lexical morphemes can be classified as, Simple, Complex and Compound, (Quebec 2022).

Simple lexical morphemes consist of a single root, such as nouns, verbs, and adverbs. Compound lexical morphemes are formed by combining two free morphemes, such as the adverb downtown (down- + -town) and the adjective gentleman (gentle- + -man). Complex lexical morphemes are composed of a root and one or more bound morphemes (affixes), such as the adverbs pavement (pave- + -ment) and imperially (imperial- + -ly); the verb looked (look- + -ed); and the adjective favored (favor- + -ed).

Table 1: Lexical Morphemes: Content Words

<i>Lexical Morphemes</i>		<i>Forms</i>	<i>Roots</i>	<i>Affixes</i>
<i>Spell</i>	Noun	<i>Simple</i>	Spell	
<i>Dry</i>	Adjective	<i>Simple</i>	Dry	
<i>Weather</i>	Noun	<i>Simple</i>	Weather	
<i>Birds</i>	Noun	<i>Complex</i>	Bird	-s
<i>Find</i>	Verb	<i>Simple</i>	Find	
<i>Very</i>	Adverb	<i>Simple</i>	Very	
<i>Little</i>	Adverb	<i>Simple</i>	Little	
<i>Drink</i>	Verb	<i>Simple</i>	Drink	
<i>Thirsty</i>	Adjective	<i>Complex</i>	Thirst	-y
<i>Crow</i>	Noun	<i>Simple</i>	Crow	
<i>Found</i>	Verb	<i>Complex</i>	f (ind)	-ound
<i>Pitcher</i>	Noun	<i>Simple</i>	Pitcher	
<i>Water</i>	Noun	<i>Simple</i>	Water	
<i>High</i>	Adjective	<i>Simple</i>	High	
<i>Narrow</i>	Adjective	<i>Simple</i>	Narrow	
<i>Neck</i>	Noun	<i>Simple</i>	Neck	
<i>Matter</i>	Noun	<i>Simple</i>	Matter	
<i>Not</i>	Adverb	<i>Simple</i>	Not	
<i>Reach</i>	Verb	<i>Simple</i>	Reach	
<i>Tried</i>	Verb	<i>Complex</i>	tr (y)	-ied
<i>Poor</i>	Adjective	<i>Simple</i>	Poor	
<i>Thing</i>	Noun	<i>Simple</i>	Thing	
<i>Felt</i>	Verb	<i>Complex</i>	fe (el)	-lt
<i>Die</i>	Verb	<i>Simple</i>	Die	
<i>Thirst</i>	Noun	<i>Simple</i>	Thirst	
<i>Idea</i>	Noun	<i>Simple</i>	Idea	
<i>Came</i>	Verb	<i>Complex</i>	c (ome)	-ame
<i>Picking</i>	Verb	<i>Complex</i>	Pick	-ing
<i>Small</i>	Adjective	<i>Simple</i>	Small	
<i>Pebbles</i>	Noun	<i>Complex</i>	Pebble	-s
<i>Dropped</i>	Verb	<i>Complex</i>	Drop	-ed
<i>Rose</i>	Verb	<i>Complex</i>	r (ise)	-ose
<i>Higher</i>	Adjective	<i>Complex</i>	High	-er
<i>Last</i>	Adjective	<i>Simple</i>	Last	
<i>Near</i>	Adverb	<i>Simple</i>	Near	
<i>Enough</i>	Adverb	<i>Simple</i>	Enough	
<i>Drink</i>	Noun	<i>Simple</i>	Drink	

The simple forms, made up of roots only, are the nouns SPELL, WEATHER, CROW, PITCHER, WATER, NECK, MATTER, THING, THIRST, IDEA, and DRINK; the adjectives are DRY, HIGH, NARROW, POOR, SMALL, and LAST; the adverbs are VERY, LITTLE, NOT, NEAR, and ENOUGH; and the verbs are FIND, DRINK, REACH, and DIE.

The complex forms made up of roots and suffixes found in the fable are two (2) nouns BIRDS and PEBBLES; 2 Adjectives THIRSTY, HIGHER; and six (6) verbs in their past FOUND, TRIED, FELT, CAME, DROPPED, ROSE and the PICKING.

From these complex forms, (1) BIRDS this plural noun is formed by adding the suffix "-s" to the singular noun "bird."; and (2) PEBBLES similarly, the plural form "pebbles" is created by adding "-s" to the singular noun "pebble"; the adjectives are (1) THIRSTY that is derived from the noun "thirst" by adding the suffix "-y," changing the word class from noun to adjective; and (2)

Morphologic Segmentation Linearity Analysis in Aesop's Fable the Crow and the Pitcher

HIGHER is a comparative adjective that is formed by adding the suffix "-er" to the adjective "high," indicating a greater degree; and the verbs (1) FOUND a past tense form of the verb "find." The complexity arises from the morphological change in the root to indicate past tense; (2) TRIED a past tense verb form adds the suffix "-ed" to the root "try," indicating a completed action; (3) FELT The word "felt" is the past tense of "feel," involving a vowel change in the root to signify past tense; (4) CAME is the past tense of "come," "came," also involves a vowel change, making it a complex form; (5) PICKING is a present participle created by adding the suffix "-ing" to the verb "pick," indicating an ongoing action; (6) DROPPED is formed by adding the suffix "-ed" to the root verb "drop," indicating past tense; and (7) ROSE, this is the past tense form of "rise," involving a vowel change to indicate past tense.

Grammatical Morphemes: Function Words

Functional morphemes are words that do not carry the content of the message but rather help the grammar of the sentence function, (Yule, 2022).

Table 2. Grammatical Morphemes: Functional words

<i>Grammatical Morphemes</i>	<i>Constituents</i>	<i>Functions in the Sentence</i>
<i>In</i>	Preposition	Indicates the context or situation: <i>In a spell; A little water "in" it.</i>
<i>A</i>	Determiner	Used as an indefinite article. It introduces nonspecific nouns: <i>a spell of dry weather; a thirsty crow; a pitcher; a little water; a narrow neck; a small pebble; a narrow neck</i>
<i>It</i>	Pronoun	Substitutes a noun. Used to refer to the pitcher: a pitcher with a little water in "it"
<i>Of</i>	Preposition	Introduces a phrase: <i>In a spell "of" dry weather; die "of" thirst.</i>
<i>When</i>	Subordinating Conjunction	Used as a conjunction to introduce a subordinate clause, indicating the time at which the main action occurs: <i>In a spell of dry weather, "when" the birds could find very little to drink...</i>
<i>The</i>	Determiner	Used as a definite article. It specifies particular nouns, making them definite and identifiable: <i>"the" Birds; "the" Pitcher; "the" water; "the" Crow; "the" poor thing</i>
<i>Could</i>	Auxiliary	Used in auxiliary function to express the ability or possibility of doing something: <i>the birds "could" find very little to drink... the Crow "could" not reach the water...</i>
<i>With</i>	Preposition	Used to indicate accompanying circumstances, means or instruments: <i>a pitcher "with" a little water in it the crow could not reach the water "with" its beak</i>
<i>But</i>	Conjunction	Used as a conjunction to introduced a contrast or exception: <i>"But" the pitcher was high... "But" the Crow could not reach the water "but" then an idea came to him</i>
<i>And</i>	Conjunction	Used to connect related ideas or action: <i>"and" no matter how he tried</i>
<i>No</i>	Determiner	used as a determiner preceding "matter," <i>"no" matter how he tried</i>
<i>How</i>	Subordinating Conjunction	Introduce clauses that explain manner or method: <i>no matter "how" he tried</i>
<i>He</i>	Pronoun	Substitutes a noun to refer to the crow: <i>"he" could not reach the water "he" must die of thirst with each pebble "he" dropped into the pitcher, the water rose a little higher</i>
<i>As</i>	Conjunction	Connects a phrase: <i>The poor thing felt "as" if he must die</i>
<i>If</i>	Conjunction	Connects a phrase: <i>The poor thing felt as "if" he must die</i>
<i>Must</i>	Auxiliary	Used in auxiliary function to indicate likelihood: <i>He felt as if he "must" die of thirst</i>
<i>Of</i>	Preposition	Used to indicate condition or state: <i>In a spell "of" dry weather; die "of" thirst</i>
<i>Then</i>	Conjunction	Used to connect two clauses: <i>The Crow couldn't reach the water, "then" an idea came to him.</i>

Morphologic Segmentation Linearity Analysis in Aesop's Fable the Crow and the Pitcher

<i>An</i>	Determiner	Used as indefinite article to indicate a noun: <i>Then "an" idea came to him</i>
<i>To</i>	Preposition	Primarily used as to indicate direction: <i>"to" drink; an idea came "to" him.</i>
<i>Him</i>	Pronoun	Substitutes a noun. Used to refer to the crow: <i>Then an idea came to "him"</i>
<i>Up</i>	Preposition	Indicates a movement or direction: <i>Picking "up" some small pebbles...</i>
<i>Them</i>	Pronoun	Replaces the noun "pebbles": <i>Picking up some small pebbles, he dropped "them" into the pitcher one by one.</i>
<i>Some</i>	Determiner	Marker of a noun: <i>Picking up "some" small pebbles</i>
<i>Into</i>	Preposition	Indicates movement: <i>He dropped "into" the pitcher</i>
<i>One</i>	Pronoun	Substitutes a noun. Used to refer to the pebble: <i>He dropped into the pitcher "one by one"</i>
<i>By</i>	Preposition	Used to indicate method or manner: <i>He dropped into the pitcher one "by" one</i>
<i>Each</i>	Determiner	Marker of a noun: With "each" pebble the water rose a little higher
<i>Until</i>	Subordinating Conjunction	Introduces the subordinate clause: <i>After dropping pebbles into the pitcher one by one, with each pebble the water rose a little higher "until" at last it was near enough so he could drink.</i>
<i>At</i>	Preposition	Introduces a phrase: <i>the water rose a little higher until "at" last it was near enough</i>
<i>Was</i>	Auxiliary	Used in auxiliary function to indicate past form: <i>a little higher until at last it "was" near enough</i>
<i>So</i>	Conjunction	Connects a phrase: <i>until at last it was near enough "so" he could drink</i>

The Determiners are used as noun markers in the selection. A, and AN used as an indefinite articles in "a" spell of dry weather; "a" thirsty crow; "a" pitcher; "a" little water; "a" narrow neck; small pebble; and an idea; while THE was used as definite article as in "the" Birds; "the" Pitcher; "the" water; "the" Crow; "the" poor thing. NO and SOME was also used as determiners to precede nouns in "no" matter how he tried and "some" small pebbles.

The Conjunctions BUT, AND, IF, THEN and SO, and functions to connect phrases and clauses found in the fable. The Subordinating Conjunction WHEN to introduce a subordinate clause, indicating the time at which the main action occurs such as In a spell of dry weather, "when" the birds could find very little to drink. The Relative Conjunction HOW function as a subordinating conjunction to introduce clauses Introduce clauses that explain manner or method: no matter "how" he tried.

The Prepositions IN, WITH, OF, TO, UP, INTO, BY and UP which introduces phrases as used in the Aesop's Fable "The Crow and The Pitcher".

Pronouns functions as substitutes of nouns found in the fable. HE, HIM refers to the Crow; IT refers to the Pitcher; and ONE refers to the Pebbles.

The Auxiliary verbs COULD function to express the ability or possibility of doing something: "the birds could find very little to drink; the Crow could not reach the water..." MUST function to indicate likelihood in statement He felt as if he "must" die of thirst and WAS function to indicate past form to be in the statement a little higher until at last it "was" near enough.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings the following generalization is arrived at: The linear morphologic segmentation of morphemic contents of Aesop's fable "The Crow and the Pitcher" reveals thirty-seven (37) lexical morphemes of twenty six (26) simple form (roots) and eleven (11) complex forms (roots with affixations) and thirty (30) grammatical morphemes broken down as follows: eight (8) prepositions, four (4) pronouns, seven (7) conjunctions, five (5) determiners, and three (3) auxiliaries. Therefore, Aesop's fable entitled "The Crow and the Pitcher" follows morphologic segmentation linearity in its narrative textuality.

The following recommendations are made in light of the findings and conclusion: (1) Knowledge of the composition of lexical and grammatical morphemes enhances one's comprehension of vocabulary. Thus, linear morphologic examination of the division of content and function words in a variety of textualities should be included in language instruction. In order to support vocabulary development, second language training should incorporate linear morphologic analysis of the segmentation of content and function terms in a variety of textualities. (3) Additional exercises pertaining to content and function words in sentences should be provided

to language learners and English majors so they may better comprehend the context of sentences, particularly when they are part of a text.

The following titles are hereby recommended to be undertaken by future linguistic researchers to better analyze the textuality of the Crow and the Pitcher: (1) A syntactical segmentation linearity of The Crow and the Pitcher, (2) A phonological segmentation linearity of The Crow and the Pitcher.

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